

8th Conference on Production Systems and Logistics

From Digital Twin Towards Shop Floor: Codeless Programming Of Pick-And-Place Robots Through Extended-Reality Interaction

Andoni Rivera-Pinto, Johan Kildal

Fundación Tekniker, Eibar, Spain

Abstract

Configuring pick-and-place robots for machine-tending tasks typically requires several days of expert programming and cell setup. This paper presents a digital-twin approach that enables non-experts to program real robots through extended-reality (XR) interaction. Within an XR environment users position the robot end effector, issue spoken commands for perception and motion planning, and automatically generate executable behaviour-tree programs deployable on a physical robot. While functional execution is demonstrated, future work will focus on quantitative accuracy validation. In a user study, novice participants completed a full six-object pick-and-place sequence in under four minutes. Compared with integrator-based workflows, the approach reduces deployment time by an order of magnitude and supports agile, human-centred automation in smart manufacturing.

Keywords

Codeless robot programming; Digital twin; Machine tending; Human–robot interaction; Agile manufacturing

1. Introduction

Industrial robots are essential for achieving flexibility and productivity in manufacturing, yet their adoption remains limited in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). A major barrier is the difficulty of configuring robots for frequently changing tasks such as part feeding, handling, and inspection. Conventional programming methods require specialised personnel who typically need to halt production, resulting in both downtime and increased integration costs. These constraints are obstacles to the practical feasibility of deploying robots for high-mix, low-volume production operations.

To address these limitations, recent research has explored intuitive human–robot interaction and programming-by-demonstration. Our earlier work [13] introduced a digital-twin-based environment where users could teach robot motions in virtual reality using hand guidance and spoken commands. The present study extends this concept to machine-tending and pick-and-place tasks, presenting an end-to-end workflow in which users program a virtual robot twin through extended-reality (XR) interaction while an executable behaviour-tree (BT) program is automatically generated. The resulting BT has been functionally deployed on a physical robot, although quantitative accuracy benchmarking between virtual and real setups remains future work. We evaluate whether non-expert users can successfully complete a full pick-and-place programming routine through this workflow in a controlled user study.

2. Related work

Programming by Demonstration (PbD) has long been studied as a strategy to enable non-experts to teach robots new skills without writing code. Classic PbD surveys describe kinaesthetic teaching, teleoperation, and multimodal demonstration techniques [2], and several collaborative robots now offer commercial kPbD functionalities. While effective for teaching basic motions, these methods typically require the robot to be taken offline [16], heavily impacting productivity.

Extended-reality (XR) interfaces have been explored as an alternative for robot programming, enabling users to specify motions or task constraints on virtual or mixed-reality representations of the robot. Prior work has demonstrated VR-based trajectory authoring, teleoperation, and workspace annotation [5]. Our earlier contributions introduced an XR environment where users could teach approach and positioning routines by manipulating a holographic digital twin and issuing spoken commands [13]. Several studies have used AR or MR interfaces for robot programming, enabling trajectory specification, waypoint annotation, or hand-guided spatial manipulation of holographic end-effectors. Examples include AR-based welding-robot programming [10, 11] and MR manipulator programming via holographic waypoints [12]. Further multimodal and digital-twin-oriented approaches explore natural manipulation of holographic robot twins, interaction through gaze and gestures, and HoloLens-based hand-guidance frameworks [3, 4].

Behaviour Trees (BTs) have become a popular representation for modular and reactive robot tasks [15]. However, few approaches exist that frame their use in production-relevant tasks [1]. Several recent works have explored automatic generation of behaviour trees for robotic task execution. For example, BTGenBot proposes generating BTs from textual task descriptions using lightweight language models [8], validating execution in simulation and on a physical robot. Similarly, CoBT generates behaviour trees from a single demonstration for manipulation tasks [9], enabling non-expert programming through demonstration-based learning. Other approaches, such as NL2BT, focus on deriving hierarchical robot skills from natural-language instructions [18] and structuring them into executable BTs. In contrast, the present work integrates XR-based interaction, digital-twin programming, machine vision, ROS2 orchestration, and automatic behaviour-tree generation into a single end-to-end programming workflow that supports functional transfer from the virtual to the physical robot.

3. Current practices to robotize a pick and place task in industry

Pick-and-place operations such as machine tending, component feeding, and part sorting, are among the most widely automated processes in industrial manufacturing. Despite this prevalence, configuring a robot for a new pick-and-place task remains a complex, multi-stage engineering effort that demands specialized expertise and significant time investment. This complexity particularly affects SMEs, which often face technical, organizational, and financial barriers when adopting advanced automation technologies [6].

The setup of a new pick-and-place application typically begins with a comprehensive analysis of the existing manual process. This includes understanding the geometry, variability, and supply method of the parts to be handled; the required cycle times; the positioning of upstream and downstream machines; and any human-robot interactions. Real production environments introduce variable conditions, such as inconsistent part orientation, mixed part types, or imperfect feeding mechanisms that must be considered from the outset.

Based on this process analysis, engineers develop the cell layout and system integration plan. Using simulation tools, they select the robot model, design the cell footprint, validate reachability and movements, and specify grippers, tools, and safety devices. Integration with external systems is also defined at this stage, including PLCs, production management software, and machine-vision components used for part detection or pose estimation. Vision configuration alone often requires careful selection and placement of cameras, calibration of coordinate frames, and design of detection strategies tailored to specific part geometries.

With the cell design complete, the next step consists of offline programming, where an initial version of the robot program is created directly from the simulated environment. This program encodes the high-level task sequence, including approach motions, pick poses, placement patterns, tool actuation and synchronization with sensors. While useful as a starting point, offline programming rarely requires additional on-site commissioning and fine-tuning due to discrepancies between the simulated and physical work cell [17].

Once the physical equipment is installed, engineers complete the setup through on-site commissioning and fine-tuning, which may require production interruptions [17]. This involves calibrating base frames and tool frames, verifying the exact pick positions under real lighting and part tolerances, refining trajectories, and resolving issues that arise from mechanical inaccuracies or environmental variation. The programming languages used (such as FANUC TPP, KUKA KRL, ABB RAPID, or URScript) are vendor-specific and require considerable training. For a typical pick-and-place application, dozens of robot positions must be manually taught and validated. Additional effort is required to calibrate cameras, test detection reliability, and adjust grasp strategies until the system achieves stable cycle times and error-free operation.

After commissioning, workers interact with the system mainly through the teach pendant interface to select production “references” or job configurations. These references may contain long lists of parameters, and similar part types often differ in subtle ways, making correct selection difficult for non-specialists. While operators can start and monitor production, they generally cannot modify or create new robot tasks; any change in part type, gripper, or process specification requires reprogramming by trained personnel.

Overall, the engineering workflow (initial task analysis, cell design, offline programming, installation, calibration, and final validation) may require several days to weeks of commissioning effort before a new pick-and-place application becomes fully operational, depending on system complexity and calibration requirements [17]. After that, adapting to changes in production demands is slow, costly, and difficult. For all these reasons, new approaches are needed for non-expert personnel to program robots more accessibly.

4. System architecture

The system architecture integrates extended-reality interaction, natural-language communication, robotic control, and machine vision into a unified framework that enables users to program and validate robotic tasks without writing code. Figure 1 illustrates the main components and information flows. The architecture follows a distributed design in which XR technologies handle user interaction and spatial task definition, while ROS2 orchestrates robotic execution, perception, and communication with the physical cell.

Figure 1: System architecture

At the core of the system is the XR scene player, responsible for executing the immersive virtual environment in which users teach robot behaviours. The XR scene player runs on a workstation connected to a VIROO® (<https://virtualwareco.com/viroo/>) server, which stores and distributes the XR scenes. The server maintains synchronized state across sessions, enabling the same virtual cell to be accessed concurrently by multiple users when required. The scene player presents the virtual workspace through an XR-HMD, providing

stereoscopic rendering, hand-controller tracking, and spatial manipulation capabilities. Users position virtual markers, define target poses, and issue task commands through direct manipulation within this environment.

Natural-language interaction is enabled through a voice dialogue system, which receives text from transcribed speech and extracts high-level task intents, action targets, and parameter references. The dialogue system operates asynchronously alongside the XR interaction loop and communicates with the XR scene player through lightweight network messages. It interprets user utterances such as “analyse the region,” “plan,” or “place the object,” mapping them to structured actions that the system can execute. This allows declarative control over robot behaviour without requiring exposure to programming syntax or low-level robot commands.

The XR subsystem communicates with ROS2, which functions as the central middleware layer governing both virtual and physical robots. ROS2 manages trajectory planning (via MoveIt 2), state updates, behaviour-tree generation, and robot-agnostic command routing. Actions triggered in the XR scene (such as movement requests, scene queries, or object interactions) are translated into ROS2 service calls or actions. The same ROS2 infrastructure is used for both simulation and real-world deployment, enabling the digital-twin paradigm in which the virtual robot mirrors the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of the physical arm. When interacting with an actual robot, ROS2 forwards joint trajectories, tool commands, and state feedback through manufacturer-specific drivers while preserving a consistent high-level interface.

Perception is provided through a machine-vision subsystem connected to ROS2. This subsystem executes object detection and geometric point extraction relevant in pick-and-place programming, such as part poses. It transmits structured observations to ROS2, which integrates them into motion-planning and execution routines. The integration via ROS2 actions ensures robust handling of asynchronous operations and allows vision data to be consumed both by the XR environment (for visualization) and by the robot controller.

Finally, the architecture connects to a physical robot, which receives planned trajectories and tool commands from ROS2. The physical robot mirrors the virtual behaviour either during execution of a recorded behaviour tree or through direct teleoperation mediated by user actions in the XR scene. Because both virtual and physical robots share the same ROS2 interfaces, switching between simulation and deployment requires no modification of the task logic, provided the virtual scene accurately reflects the real-world configuration.

Overall, the architecture combines immersive XR-based programming, natural-language interaction, robot-agnostic control, and integrated perception into a cohesive system that lowers the complexity of robotic application development.

5. Interaction workflow

The interaction workflow enables users to program a complete pick-and-place task directly within the XR environment by combining spatial manipulation, natural-language commands, and automatic program generation. Inside the virtual cell, the user manipulates a virtual pose marker (a red sphere with an arrow) using the motion-tracked controllers. The user positions this marker above the region of interest, thus defining the desired end-effector pose for viewing the parts scattered on the table.

Once the pose is set, the user triggers motion planning through the spoken command “*plan*”. The planned trajectory is visualized in XR, and, if satisfactory, the user confirms execution with “*execute the plan*”, causing the virtual robot to move its onboard camera to the marked viewpoint. With the robot observing the workspace, the user requests perception by saying “*analyse the region of interest*”. This prompts the machine-vision subsystem to detect all parts and extract their geometric features. The XR environment displays the processed image and detected poses for user verification. The user specifies the desired placement arrangement verbally using natural expressions, such as: “*place the nuts in a matrix of three rows and two columns.*” From this directive, the system automatically works out the placement targets and computes the full pick-and-place sequence, including approach, grasp, transfer, and placement motions

As these interactions occur, the system records the user's actions, pose selections, and spoken commands, and automatically compiles them into a behaviour tree representing the complete robot program. The behaviour tree captures the structure of the task and references the same actions used during interaction. Because both the virtual and physical robots share the same ROS2 interfaces, the resulting program can be executed on the real robot without modification, provided the virtual scene reflects the physical setup. The generated behaviour tree was deployed and executed on the physical robot, successfully completing the full six-object pick-and-place sequence. This demonstrates functional transfer from the digital twin to the shop-floor setup. However, quantitative benchmarking of positional accuracy and calibration deviations between the virtual and physical environments remains future work.

This workflow therefore provides an efficient path from intuitive XR-based task definition to deployable pick-and-place behaviour, greatly reducing the technical barriers associated with traditional robot programming.

6. Evaluation in user study

The system was evaluated through a user study designed to examine whether non-expert participants could program a complete pick-and-place routine using the XR-based workflow and whether the interaction demands remained compatible with rapid deployment in production contexts.

6.1 Participants

Twelve participants were recruited from engineering and research staff and postgraduate students. Five participants were female. All held university degrees, with backgrounds including robotics, computer science, industrial engineering and machine vision. The group showed varied levels of prior experience with XR systems and collaborative robots. However, they were non-experts in industrial robot programming, as none had prior experience with vendor-specific teach-pendant programming or behaviour-tree-based task specification. All participants opted in voluntarily and provided informed consent.

6.2 Procedure

The study took place entirely in the virtual cell recreated in XR (see Figure 2). Participants were first familiarised with the system and then completed one measured trial. The task consisted of programming a collaborative robot to perform a six-object pick-and-place routine: analysing a disordered set of nuts and washers in a region of interest, identifying required parts through a voice-triggered vision analysis, and commanding the robot to place selected nuts into a 3×2 matrix arrangement.

Figure 2: Virtual cell environment. The robot is creating the specified pattern through pick and place.

Participants interacted with the robot through two modalities:

- **Hand-guided positioning** of the end-effector proxy (a holographic sphere with an orientation arrow) above the region of interest (procedure to set the starting position).
- **Spoken instructions** interpreted by the dialogue system, for the execution of actions such as conducting a visual analysis of the unarranged parts, displaying previews of planned actions.

6.3 Quantitative and qualitative metrics

Three quantitative measures were collected:

- **Task completion time:** total time from the start of programming until the virtual execution of the full 2×3 pick-and-place sequence.
- **Single Ease Question (SEQ)** [14]: 7-point rating of perceived ease of completing the programming task.
- **NASA-TLX (raw)** [7]: subjective workload as an index and across six dimensions.

Participants provided comments regarding usability in a semi-structured interview at the end of the study.

6.4 Results

All twelve participants successfully completed the task. The mean programming time was under four minutes (mean 196.3 s, SD 20.9 s). See distribution of observed times in Figure 3. This value includes the entire programming cycle, from initial positioning of the end effector to the robot completing the full six-object placement routine in the virtual twin. An expert user performed the same cycle in approximately 90 seconds, indicating that the interaction overhead decreases with familiarity.

Figure 3: Distribution of completion times for the pick-and-place programming task (N = 12).

Subjective ratings were highly positive. Participants reported high ease of task completion (mean SEQ 5.58/7; see Figure 4). Rated workload was also low (mean NASA-TLX index 3.78/10; see Figure 5).

Figure 4. Single Ease Question (SEQ) scores for the pick-and-place programming task (N = 12). Scale ranges from 1 (very difficult) to 7 (very easy)

In the end-of study semi-structured interview, participants consistently reported two sources of difficulty, which contributed to time variance across participants:

- **Grabbing and positioning the holographic end-effector proxy** required more precision than some users initially expected. Minor misalignments occasionally required repositioning.
- **Dialogue-system interpretation errors** occurred when speech was unclear or delivered too quickly, which required repeating spoken instructions.

Across the twelve trials, the dialogue system produced approximately 10 command misinterpretations in total, requiring occasional repetitions of spoken instructions (less than one retry per participant on average). Despite these interaction errors, all participants successfully completed the full six-object pick-and-place routine without external assistance, indicating functional robustness of the overall programming workflow. In the end-of-study interviews, several participants emphasised that natural-language interaction was one of the most intuitive aspects of the workflow.

Figure 5: NASA-TLX workload scores for the pick-and-place programming task (N = 12).

7. Discussion

The results show that non-expert users can program a complete pick-and-place routine in a digital-twin environment in under four minutes, a timescale fundamentally different from current industrial practice. As

described earlier, configuring a new pick-and-place application typically requires multiple stages (process analysis, cell design, offline programming, physical commissioning, and final calibration) which often accumulate to more than two weeks before a functional solution is deployed. While the XR workflow presented here does not eliminate the mechanical integration and safety-critical components of this process, it substantially reduces the task-definition and programming effort traditionally performed via simulation software and a teach pendant. The capacity to define robot behaviour interactively and generate an executable behaviour tree aligns well with industrial demands for faster reconfiguration in high-mix environments.

The findings also suggest that the workflow scales well across users with diverse technical backgrounds. Variability in completion times remained relatively small, and subjective workload was low across all NASA-TLX dimensions. This consistency indicates that the interactive system design (combining spatial manipulation, natural-language instructions, and automatic program generation) reduces the cognitive burden associated with traditional robot programming. Users could focus on specifying task intent rather than navigating manufacturer-specific programming languages.

Nevertheless, several limitations must be addressed before broad industrial deployment. Speech-based interaction, although intuitive, showed occasional misinterpretations when commands were delivered rapidly. Improving robustness may be necessary in noisy shop-floor environments. While functional execution of the generated behaviour tree on the physical robot has been demonstrated, the current study does not quantify positional accuracy, calibration sensitivity, or tolerance accumulation between the virtual and the real setups. These aspects will be addressed in future industrial validation studies. It is likely that accurate transfer of virtual task definition to the physical cell will depend on the fidelity of the digital twin, discrepancies in calibration, lighting, or part presentation.

From a deployment perspective, additional considerations include calibration fidelity between virtual and physical coordinate frames, robustness of speech recognition under industrial noise conditions, and compliance with safety standards when integrating with PLC-controlled production lines. Accurate base and tool calibration will be critical to ensure reliable execution, particularly in tasks with tight tolerances. Furthermore, integration into certified industrial environments may require additional safeguards and validation steps beyond those evaluated in this study.

In addition, participants were recruited from engineering and research staff rather than from shop-floor operators. Although they were non-experts in industrial robot programming, further studies with production personnel are required to confirm the generalisability of the approach to typical industrial end-users. Similarly, the current study focused on a single robot and a constrained pick-and-place scenario. Thus, broader validation is also needed across different cell layouts and part types.

Despite these limitations, the approach demonstrates strong potential for reducing reconfiguration time and enabling operators with limited programming expertise to adapt robotic tasks rapidly. This supports ongoing efforts towards agile and human-centred automation in manufacturing.

8. Conclusions and future steps

This work presented a digital-twin based approach to enabling non-experts to program pick-and-place tasks through extended-reality. In the system described, the user utilizes kinaesthetic demonstration of actions in the robotic cell together with providing natural-language instructions for the robot to execute a pick and place task. These interactions with the virtual robot produce executable behaviour-tree programs that have been successfully deployed on a physical robot, while accuracy benchmarking remains future work.

In a controlled user study, participants required under four minutes to create and validate a complete six-object pick and place task programming routine, reporting low workload and high ease of use. These results

indicate that immersive programming interfaces can significantly reduce the effort associated with configuring collaborative robots for frequently changing tasks.

Future work will expand this approach to additional scenarios that are also frequently found in industry. Further research will also explore deployment in live pilot cells to evaluate performance under real production conditions. This will include operator variability, environmental disturbances (e.g., noise, non-ideal lighting conditions) and integration with upstream and downstream production processes. Overall, the results suggest that XR-based programming combined with behaviour-tree execution may provide a promising human-centred and inclusive approach to robotic systems programming.

Acknowledgements

This work has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101093079 (MASTER).

References

- [1] Akkaladevi, S.C., Propst, M., Deshpande, K., Hofmann, M. and Pichler, A. 2024. Towards a behavior tree based robotic skill execution framework for human robot collaboration in industrial assembly. 2024 10th International Conference on Automation, Robotics and Applications (ICARA) (2024), 18–22.
- [2] Argall, B.D., Chernova, S., Veloso, M. and Browning, B. 2009. A survey of robot learning from demonstration. *Robotics and autonomous systems*. 57, 5 (2009), 469–483.
- [3] Chu, C.-H. and Lee, I.-Y. 2025. An Experimental Study on the Design of Interaction Modalities in Augmented Reality for Industrial Robot Programming. *Journal of Computing and Information Science in Engineering*. 25, 5 (2025), 051005.
- [4] Chu, C.-H. and Weng, C.-Y. 2024. Experimental analysis of augmented reality interfaces for robot programming by demonstration in manufacturing. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*. 74, (2024), 463–476.
- [5] Devic, A., Vidakovic, J. and Zivkovic, N. 2024. Development of Standalone Extended-Reality-Supported Interactive Industrial Robot Programming System. *Machines*. 12, 7 (2024), 480.
- [6] Elhousseiny, H.M. and Crispim, J. 2022. SMEs, Barriers and Opportunities on adopting Industry 4.0: A Review. *Procedia Computer Science*. 196, (2022), 864–871.
- [7] Hart, S. and Staveland, L. 1988. Development of NASA-TLX (Task Load Index): Results of Empirical and Theoretical Research. *Human Mental Workload*. P. Hancock and N. Meshkati, eds. Elsevier Science Publishers B.V. 139–183.
- [8] Izzo, R.A., Bardaro, G. and Matteucci, M. 2024. Btgenbot: Behavior tree generation for robotic tasks with lightweight llms. 2024 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS) (2024), 9684–9690.
- [9] Jain, A., Long, P., Villani, V., Kelleher, J.D. and Leva, M.C. 2024. Cobt: Collaborative programming of behaviour trees from one demonstration for robot manipulation. 2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA) (2024), 12993–12999.
- [10] Ni, D., Nee, A., Ong, S., Li, H., Zhu, C. and Song, A. 2018. Point cloud augmented virtual reality environment with haptic constraints for teleoperation. *Transactions of the Institute of Measurement and Control*. 40, 15 (Nov. 2018), 4091–4104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0142331217739953>.
- [11] Ni, D., Yew, A.W.W., Ong, S.K. and Nee, A.Y.C. 2017. Haptic and visual augmented reality interface for programming welding robots. *Advances in Manufacturing*. 5, 3 (2017), 191–198.
- [12] Ostanin, M., Zaitsev, S., Sabirova, A. and Klimchik, A. 2022. Interactive Industrial Robot Programming based on Mixed Reality and Full Hand Tracking. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*. 55, 10 (2022), 2791–2796.

- [13] Rivera-Pinto, A., Kildal, J., Aceta, C., Castillo, A. and Aizpurua, G. 2025. Codeless Teaching of Robot-Arm Positioning in VR. *European Robotics Forum 2025* (2025), 42–47.
- [14] Sauro, J. 2011. *A Practical Guide to the System Usability Scale: Background, Benchmarks & Best Practices*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- [15] Shin, M. and Jung, S. 2024. A Survey of Behavior Tree-Based Task Planning Algorithms for Autonomous Robotic Systems. *2024 15th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)* (2024), 2039–2041.
- [16] Sosa-Ceron, A.D., Gonzalez-Hernandez, H.G. and Reyes-Avenidaño, J.A. 2022. Learning from Demonstrations in Human–Robot Collaborative Scenarios: A Survey. *Robotics*. 11, 6 (Dec. 2022), 126. <https://doi.org/10.3390/robotics11060126>.
- [17] Tanz, L. and Daub, R. 2022. Automated commissioning of offline-generated robot programs. *Procedia CIRP*. 107, (2022), 810–814.
- [18] Wang, K., Zhao, Y., Dai, S., Yang, M., He, Y. and Zhang, N. 2024. NL2BT: Learning Hierarchical Robot Skills Represented by Behavior Trees from Natural Language. *Cooperative Information Systems*. M. Sellami, M.-E. Vidal, B. Van Dongen, W. Gaaloul, and H. Panetto, eds. Springer Nature Switzerland. 366–383.

Biography

Andoni Rivera-Pinto is a researcher in human robot interaction at Tekniker. He obtained his PhD at University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) in 2025, with research on multimodal XR based interactions to program robots by demonstration. He is driving technical XR developments in various National and European research projects.

Johan Kildal obtained his PhD in multimodal Human-computer interaction at the University of Glasgow 2008. In the period 2008-2016, he was principal researcher at the Nokia Research Center in Helsinki, developing future interactive solutions and technologies. Since 2016, he is coordinating and contributing to National and European research and development projects, with a focus on XR technologies in the factory of the future.